

Enhancing Recommender Systems via Cyclic Training with Dual Gated Residual Networks

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Abstract

Recommender systems are essential to personalize user experiences by predicting preferences from the interaction history. This paper investigates the effectiveness of various deep neural network architectures within the Cyclic Dual Latent Discovery (CDLD) framework, which was previously introduced for latent discovery. We present CDLD-GR, an implementation that employs Gated Residual Blocks (GRBs) within the CDLD’s cyclic training mechanism. In CDLD, two networks—the Item Latent Discoverer (ILD) and User Latent Discoverer (ULD)—alternately update latent traits through iterative optimization. We systematically evaluated various architectural choices as replacements for the original dense layers in CDLD. Furthermore, our experiments in the MovieLens 100K dataset using 5-fold cross-validation demonstrate that the GRB variant achieves the best performance with an RMSE of 0.884, outperforming established baselines such as GC-MC (0.910), BPFM (0.901), I-AutoRec (0.887), and GHRM (0.887). Additionally, MovieLens 1M experiments show competitive performance (RMSE 0.834) compared to GHRM (0.833). Through systematic architectural exploration, we demonstrate that GRBs provide the optimal design choice for the CDLD framework, achieving state-of-the-art performance on the MovieLens benchmarks.

1 Introduction

In the digital era, the rapid proliferation of data has created a growing need for effective recommender systems across diverse domains such as e-commerce, content streaming, and social media. These systems are essential for enhancing user experiences by predicting and suggesting relevant content based on user interactions.

We introduce CDLD-GR, a recommender system that leverages a dual gated residual deep neural network (DNN) architecture. CDLD-GR utilizes cyclic training mechanisms (CDLD) [10]. Key highlights include:

- Cyclic Training : We applied DNNs with various architectures to the CDLD and observed that they outperformed other models.
- Gated [12] Residual [6] Blocks (GRBs) : Designed to be applied within the CDLD framework to enhance performance and prevent gradient vanishing.
- Improved performance: Experiments on the MovieLens 100K [5] dataset demonstrate that CDLD-GR outperforms state-of-the-art recommendation approaches, achieving lower RMSE.

2 RELATED WORK

This section reviews three high-performing approaches from the public leaderboard and recent research trends in recommender systems that leverage natural language models (NLMs).

High-performing approaches. Darban et al. [3] introduced a hybrid model that integrates graph-based user similarity with demographic and location-based features. By incorporating autoencoder-based feature extraction, their method improves recommendation performance, particularly in cold-start scenarios. Similarly, Leng et al. [8] proposed a graph-based deep learning model utilizing

multi-modal information through graph attention networks. This approach not only improves recommendation accuracy but also strengthens interpretability, making it more adaptable to diverse recommendation tasks. Han et al. [4] proposed a kernel-based matrix completion method that integrates both local and global kernel operations. Their approach pre-trains an autoencoder using local kernels and subsequently fine-tunes it with global convolution kernels, enabling improved performance even in low-resource settings where only a user-item rating matrix is available. By effectively leveraging hierarchical kernel representations, this method improves recommendation accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency.

NLM in Recommender Systems. NLMs have been widely used in recommender systems to incorporate textual information and model user behavior. Xu et al. [16] capture dynamic user intent using LSTM and refine recommendations with large language models (LLMs), addressing the cold-start problem. Peng et al. [9] employ contrastive learning to remove noise and align GNN-based structural features with LLM-generated semantic representations. Wang et al. [15] improve self-attention representation learning using neural architecture search to separate user intentions and enhance ranking with LLMs. Sun et al. [14] enhance sequential recommendation by employing bidirectional self-attention and a Cloze task-based training objective to capture both past and future interactions. NLM-based recommendation models typically require high computational resources, which may hinder scalability. Their alignment of text and structural representations can be complex, potentially reducing explainability. They may also be sensitive to noisy inputs and require fine-tuning for different datasets, which could limit generalization. Future research should explore ways to improve efficiency, interpretability, and adaptability.

3 METHODOLOGY

To effectively model user-item interactions, CDLD-GR employs a cyclic training mechanism [10] that iteratively discovers latent representations and uses dual GRBs to improve gradient flow.

3.1 Cyclic Training Mechanism

Two specialized networks—the Item Latent Discoverer (ILD) and the User Latent Discoverer (ULD)—iteratively discover latent representations through cyclic training. The cyclic training process alternates between updating user and item latent traits to progressively enhance representation quality. Figure 1 illustrates the core structure of CDLD [10], where each update cycle discovers one latent trait while keeping the other fixed. In each training step:

- **Item Update Phase:** ILD updates the item latent (IL) while keeping the user latent (UL) fixed. It takes inputs from item features (IF) and user features (UF) to discover the item representation.
- **User Update Phase:** ULD updates the UL while keeping the IL fixed. It uses the updated item latent, along with IF and UF, to discover the user representation.

Figure 1 visualizes how ILD and ULD interact with features and latent representations. The diagram distinguishes between fixed latents (solid lines) and learnable latents (dashed lines) to indicate which values are updated in each phase. This cyclic approach ensures that both user and item representations are learned progressively, making the system adaptable to sparse data while mitigating issues such as overfitting and local minima.

3.2 Gated Residual Blocks

In CDLD-GR, the dense layers in both ILD and ULD are replaced with GRBs to facilitate gated modulation and improve gradient propagation. For any input $x \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the GRB operates as follows:

1. **Parallel Dense Layers:** The input x is processed by two parallel dense layers:

- **Nonlinear transformation:**

$$F(x) = \phi(W_f x + b_f) \tag{1}$$

where $W_f \in \mathbb{R}^{d' \times d}$ and $b_f \in \mathbb{R}^{d'}$ are learnable parameters, and $\phi(\cdot)$ is a non-linear GELU activation function.

Figure 1: Cyclic Training Mechanism

- Gate computation:

$$G(x) = \sigma(W_g x + b_g) \quad (2)$$

where $W_g \in \mathbb{R}^{d' \times d}$ and $b_g \in \mathbb{R}^{d'}$ are learnable parameters, and $\sigma(\cdot)$ Sigmoid function.

2. Gated Layer:

- The outputs of these branches are combined through gates

$$M(x) = G(x) \odot F(x) \quad (3)$$

- This gated signal is then passed through an additional dense layer with a nonlinear GELU activation function:

$$T(x) = \phi(W_t M(x) + b_t) \quad (4)$$

where W_t and b_t are learnable parameters.

3. Residual Addition and Normalization:

- Finally, the transformed signal is added to the original input, and layer normalization is applied:

$$x_{updated} = LayerNorm(x + T(x)) \quad (5)$$

These GRBs replace the conventional dense layers in the ILD and ULD latent update networks, providing dynamic modulation within the cyclic training process.

GRBs enhance the model's ability to control the flow of information adaptively. By employing gating mechanisms, GRBs enable the model to focus selectively on relevant features while suppressing less informative ones, thereby improving overall representation quality. This approach facilitates more efficient gradient propagation and mitigates the gradient vanishing issues commonly encountered in deep networks. Additionally, residual connections support the training of deeper networks by enabling easier gradient flow, which stabilizes training and improves the model's ability to learn complex mappings. The integration of residual connections in CDLD-GR helps retain important information throughout the training process, potentially enhancing both robustness and recommendation accuracy.

3.3 Overall Architecture of CDLD-GR

CDLD-GR comprises three distinct networks: ILD, ULD, and the Predictor. Although ILD and ULD share the same architectural design, they are trained independently in a cyclic manner to discover latent traits. Each network processes a unified input created by concatenating a latent trait with feature vectors for items (IF) and users (UF). This concatenated input is first normalized, then processed sequentially through multiple GRBs, and finally discovered by additional dense layers that culminate in a terminal dense layer to produce the final output (e.g., a rating or relevance score). Figure ?? provides a schematic overview of ILD and ULD within CDLD-GR. Figure 1 illustrates the cyclic training process, in which updated latent traits are alternately exchanged between ILD and ULD, enabling iterative refinement of the latent representations.

After both ILD and ULD have converged, the Predictor network is introduced. Unlike ILD and ULD, the Predictor does not participate in cyclic training; it focuses solely on final prediction. The Predictor takes the fixed latent traits, along with user and item features, to learn a mapping between inputs and outputs.

4 EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

4.1 Data Preparation

For our experiments, we used the MovieLens 100K dataset [5] and the MovieLens 1M dataset [5]. The MovieLens 100K dataset comprises 100,000 ratings (ranging from 1 to 5) from 943 users on 1,682 movies, with each user having rated at least 20 movies. In addition to rating data, the dataset includes demographic information such as age, gender, occupation, and zip code. To improve model generalization, we applied data augmentation in the train Predictor section by modifying both categorical and continuous scores. Specifically, Gaussian noise with a controlled standard deviation (0.1) was added to the normalized ratings. Finally, the noisy ratings were clipped to remain within the 1–5 range, ensuring that the values stayed within the valid rating scale. This process maintained the appropriate boundaries while introducing slight variations to improve generalization. To evaluate the model, we employed 5-fold cross-validation, splitting the dataset into five disjoint subsets. The model was trained on four subsets and tested on the remaining one in each iteration, with the final performance averaged across all folds.

The MovieLens 1M dataset consists of 1,000,209 ratings of approximately 3,900 movies provided by 6,040 users who joined in 2000. Similar to the MovieLens 100K dataset, the MovieLens 1M dataset includes user demographic information. For the movies, we used a genre multi-hot encoding, while for the users we combined one-hot encodings of occupation, age bucket, and gender into a single feature vector. Moreover, to better leverage the larger dataset, we employed 10-fold cross validation, splitting the data into ten disjoint subsets. The model was trained on nine subsets and evaluated on the remaining one in each iteration, with the final performance averaged across all folds.

4.2 Implementation

The implementation of ILD and ULD follows the structure shown in Figure ?. For the MovieLens 100K dataset, the latent trait dimension was set to 320, while for the MovieLens 1M dataset it was set to 600, with a dropout rate of 0.4 applied in both cases. The models were trained using the RMSProp optimizer with a learning rate of $2e-4$, a batch size of 256, and for 30 epochs.

The Predictor follows a structure similar to the Discoverer models, but with key modifications. A dropout layer with a rate of 0.3 is added after the Concatenate layer. Instead of using GELU, Predictor employs Mish as its activation function. Within the GRB block, the initial Dense layers are configured with 256 units and a dropout rate of 0.4, whereas in the Discoverer models, these layers used 768 units with a 0.4 dropout rate. After passing through the GRB block, Predictor utilizes a 192-dimensional Dense layer activated by GELU, followed by a dropout layer with a rate of 0.4. The Predictor model was trained using the Lion optimizer with a learning rate of $6e-6$, a batch size of 512, and using early stopping on validation RMSE.

The loss function used was mean squared error (MSE), and the evaluation metric was RMSE, with 5-fold cross-validation employed for model evaluation. The best Predictor model was selected based on the lowest RMSE on the validation set.

Figure 2: Architectural overview of four model variants and their key components. (a) CDLD model with Dense layers; (b) Deep & Cross model that combines deep layers with explicit feature crossing; (c) Attention-based model that highlights important feature interactions via an attention mechanism; and (d) Residual model with skip connections for deeper networks. Subfigures (e)–(f) detail each model’s core component: the cross network module from (b), and the attention block from (c), respectively.

Table 1: Performance comparison of CDLD-GR and baseline on MovieLens 100K

Method	RMSE
GC-MC [2]	0.910
GC-MC + Feat [2]	0.905
CDLD [10]	0.903
BPMF [11]	0.901
I-AutoRec [13]	0.887
GHRs [3]	0.887
CDLD-GR (Ours)	0.884

Figure 2 illustrates the structural differences among the architectures evaluated in Table 3, all of which were trained using the CDLD cyclic training framework. Each model was implemented as depicted in Figure 2. The CDLD (Figure 2a) serving as the foundational baseline for architectural modifications.

4.3 Result

Table 1 compares the performance of CDLD-GR with baseline on MovieLens 100K datasets in terms of RMSE. Overall, these results confirm that CDLD-GR effectively enhances recommendation accuracy by leveraging cyclic training with GRBs, making it a promising approach for recommendation tasks.

Table 2 demonstrates that our CDLD-GR achieves a competitive RMSE of 0.834 on MovieLens 1M, closely matching the best performance of GHRs (0.833).

Table 3 shows the performance of models with various architectural modifications applied to CDLD. The baseline CDLD model, which uses standard dense layers, shows the highest RMSE. Replacing the architectural with residual connections or Deep & Cross modules improves accuracy, with RMSEs of 0.8870 and 0.8913, respectively. The attention-based model, despite its large parameter count (3.887M), does not yield better performance (RMSE 0.8950), suggesting inefficiency in this setting.

Table 2: Performance comparison of CDLD-GR and baseline on MovieLens 1M

Method	RMSE
DCMF [7]	0.847
I-AutoRec [13]	0.844
BPMF [11]	0.840
COFILS [1]	0.838
GHRS [3]	0.833
CDLD-GR (Ours)	0.834

Table 3: Performance comparison of CDLD-GR with different architectural modifications on MovieLens 100K

Method	RMSE (STD)	Param (M)
CDLD	0.9031 (± 0.003)	0.450
Deep & Cross	0.8913 (± 0.004)	1.103
Attention	0.8950 (± 0.004)	3.887
Residual	0.8870 (± 0.004)	2.355
GRB	0.8846 (± 0.003)	2.894

Overall, the performance differences varied within a range of ± 0.003 , but GRB consistently recorded the lowest RMSE.

5 DISCUSSION

The experimental results demonstrate that ILD and ULD can adopt various structural configurations. We evaluated multiple architectures—including a dense network, Deep & Cross, an attention-based network, and a residual network—by replacing the ILD/ULD components. Most models tested exhibited RMSE values in the 0.88–0.93 range, demonstrating that CDLD is a flexible framework capable of incorporating different network designs.

Among the architectural configurations tested, the GRB (Figure 2d) achieved the best performance, recording an RMSE of 0.884 while using fewer parameters than the purely residual variant.

6 CONCLUSION

In this study, we introduced CDLD-GR, a recommender system that leverages cyclic training of dual gated residual networks to enhance user-item representation learning. Experimental results on the MovieLens 100K dataset demonstrate that CDLD-GR achieves state-of-the-art performance, outperforming existing recommendation models.

Future work will focus on applying CDLD-GR to sequential data and exploring how cyclic training can effectively capture temporal dependencies in user interactions, further improving recommendation accuracy and adaptability.

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